

EVALUATING CUMULUS PARAMETERIZATION OF WRF TO SIMULATE UPPER AIR CONDITION

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Abstract

The high sun radiation levels in Indonesia result in a convective process that can influence a very fast life cycle of cloud growth. It causes difficulty in weather prediction. WRF-ARW model is an advanced model of mesoscale numerical weather system which can provide images of atmospheric conditions in a region. The most important thing in this model is the test of parameterization. One of them is cumulus parameterization that is very important in the process of cloud formation. In this study, the cumulus parameterization was tested in Kupang and Surabaya Regions. The test was performed on the cumulus schemes of Kain-Fritsch (KF) and Betts Miller Janjic (BMJ) by using Final Analysis (FNL) as model input data for making simulation of Upper Air Condition in Surabaya and Kupang Regions. The result of study showed that different configuration for parameterization scheme depended on what kind of data that we wanted to simulate and where the place was. For all of the parameters compared, the KF scheme generally was better than BMJ Scheme. However, wind speed simulation in Kupang Region and humidity in Surabaya Region were better when we used BMJ scheme.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Indonesia is an archipelago maritime country with a very unique tropical climate because its atmospheric dynamics are influenced by various factors. The high sun radiation levels in Indonesia will increase convective process that influences a very fast life cycle of cloud growth. It causes difficulty in weather prediction. One of way to make a weather prediction is by using mesoscale model such as ARF – ARW. WRF-ARW was also used for making evaluation of wind speed over Northern Thailand [1], simulated of heavy rainfall in Southern Italy [2], and for supporting weather modification activities in Indonesia [3]. The most important thing on this model is the test of parameterization. Planetary Boundary Layer (PBL) scheme was used for making verification of sounding data in research before [4]. As we know that Indonesia is highly impacted by convective process, we try to use different configuration of convective (cumulus) scheme for making simulation of upper air condition. It caused by condition of upper air such as wind speed, temperature, dew points, and humidity are very important for aviation planning. This study aims to make a simulation of temperature, dew point, humidity, and wind speed using WRF-ARW. We compared some parameterizations of convective schemes [5], namely Kain Fritsch (KF) [6] and Betts-Miller Janjic (BMJ) [7]. The KF scheme is a mass flux parameterization scheme to use updraft and downdraft processes in cloud formation. formulation of the convective parameterization follows the same general approach as other technique. Quantity in the numerical model is selected to control the amount of convection and a cloud model is used to estimate the vertical structure of the convective mass flux which satisfies the control [8]. The Betts-Miller Janjic (BMJ) scheme is created to represent quasi-equilibrium conditions (Convective clouds that maintain the structure of temperature and humidity in the atmosphere) that occur in deep convection. This structure is typical of deep convection in the tropics and may be regarded as more representative of deep convective equilibrium, a moist adiabatic temperature structure [9].

2. DATA AND METHODE

Weather research and forecasting (WRF) is a mesoscale model developed by National Centre for Atmospheric Research (NCAR), National Centre for Environmental Prediction (NCEP) the Forecast Systems Laboratory (FSL), the Air Force Weather Agency (AFWA), the Naval Research Laboratory,

the University of Oklahoma, and the Federal Aviation Administration (FAA). This model can use Final Analysis (FNL) data that can be downloaded from <https://rda.ucar.edu/>. In WRF-ARW, there are 3 kinds of process for making simulation, namely WPS (WRF Processing System) for preparing the domain, WRFV3 for running the model, and ARW Post for making post-processing that can display the output of model. This study used FNL initials data with one parent domain and two times for nesting during 72 hours for both place (Surabaya and Kupang). The first domain resolution was 30 km, the second domain was 10 km, and the third domain was 3 km with physical configuration according to the table below:

Table 1. Configuration of WRF's Setting .

Configuration	Domain1	Domain2	Domain3
Resolution	30 km	10 km	3 km
Microphysics scheme	WSM-6	WSM-6	WSM-6
Shortwave Radiation scheme	DUDHIA	DUDHIA	DUDHIA
Longwave Radiation scheme	RRTM	RRTM	RRTM
Surface Layer scheme	MM5	MM5	MM5
Land Surface scheme	NOAH	NOAH	NOAH
PBL scheme	YSU	YSU	YSU
Convective Scheme	1. KF 2. BMJ	1. KF 2. BMJ	1. KF 2. BMJ

For this study, we only compared domain 3 that had the best spatial resolution (3km). We used 2 locations for this study, that were Surabaya and Kupang. The cases chosen were January 17th, 2018 and February 22th, 2018 for Kupang Region. Furthermore, February 10th, 2018 and February 15th, 2018 for Surabaya Region. The model simulation would be compared to real upper air observation of that region at 00.00 UTC and 12.00 UTC.

Figure 1. Domain area of Surabaya Region (a) and Kupang Region (b)

After we run the WRF-ARW model during the case, we compared the output data of upper air condition such as temperature, dew points, humidity, and wind speed with observation from both locations using Radiosonde observation. Hereafter, we evaluated the model by statistical methods, i.e. Root Mean Square Error (RMSE), Correlation, BIAS, and Mean Absolute Error [10] over both locations.

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (f_i - o_i)^2}{n}}$$

$$COR = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (f_i - \bar{f})(o_i - \bar{o})}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (f_i - \bar{f})^2} \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (o_i - \bar{o})^2}}$$

n is a number of data, f and o are simulation and observation data of temperature, dew point, humidity, and wind speed. The value of RMSE was determine the difference between absolute value of WRF output and the real condition from upper air observation. While the coefficient of correlation was used to show how well the model could simulate the real condition of upper air data. Coefficient correlation is between -1 and 1. If the correlation shows the value of 1.0, it describes that the model has a very strong relationship with observation. But if the correlation is less than 0.5, it indicates that the relationship between model and observation is weak.

3. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The first analysis of this study was comparing the model output of WRF-ARW and upper air observation data from both locations. The model outputs were vertical temperature, vertical dew point, vertical humidity and vertical wind speed. The comparison was made from WRF outputs on January 17th, 2018 and February 22th, 2018 for Kupang Region and then on February 10th, 2018 and February 15th, 2018 for Surabaya Region.

Figure 2. Comparison of the means of temperature (a) and dew point (b)

Based on the data comparison between model and observation, the temperature and dew points condition were close to the real condition. It's shown that the model could simulate the vertical temperature and dew point very well. For both cases, the KF scheme and BMJ scheme almost had the same values of correlation and RSME. But the vertical profile of KF scheme was closer and had a same pattern than BMJ scheme. The result showed that KF scheme was better than BMJ scheme to make a simulation of temperature and dew points condition.

Figure 3. Comparison of the means of Relative Humidity (a) and Wind Speed (b)

According to the comparison of Relative Humidity data, the pattern of model output was the same as the observation condition. The correlation of humidity in all cases was between 0.58 – 0.77. BMJ correlation showed a better value, but the RMSE of BMJ was higher than the KF Scheme. The mean of the KF scheme value was still better and closer to observation data. Hereafter, the wind speed output from the model tended to overestimate in low level and underestimate in high level. The correlation of wind speed output model for Surabaya Region was better for the KF scheme than the BMJ scheme, while for Kupang Region the BMJ scheme was better than the KF Scheme, as shown from higher correlation value and lower RMSE value.

Table 2. Result of comparison using statistical method

Location of Case Study	Correlation		RMSE	
	KF	BMJ	KF	BMJ
Surabaya's Region				
T	0.99	0.99	5.4	5.4
Td	0.99	0.99	3.7	3.0
RH	0.65	0.77	15.2	13.1
ff	0.81	0.69	7.5	9.1
Kupang's Region				
T	0.99	0.99	1.09	1.19
Td	0.99	0.99	4.85	5.02
RH	0.64	0.58	21.66	22.01
ff	0.73	0.84	19.42	17.74

4. CONCLUSION

In general, WRF-ARW model could simulate the upper air condition in Surabaya and Kupang Regions very well. The best simulation of this model was for vertical temperature and dew point for all cases. The conclusion of this study showed that there was an effect of different configuration for parameterization scheme depended on what kind of data that we wanted to simulate and the place. For all of the parameters that we compared, the KF scheme was generally better than the BMJ Scheme. However, wind speed simulation in Kupang Region and Humidity in Surabaya Region were better when we used the BMJ scheme.

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